

National Cultural Heritage Through Hebei Folk Song Education among School Choir: Psychological Well-being Survey

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: May 11, 2022</p> <p>Accepted: December 13, 2022</p> <p>Keywords : National Cultural Heritage, Hebei Folk Education, School Choir</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7434346</p>	<p><i>Hebei folk songs refer to the folk music spread in Hebei Province. Their representative works include "Little Cattle Release", "Going Back to Her Mother's Home" and "Little Cabbage". Hebei folk song is an ancient kind of Han folk music. Is plain, honest, or solemn, and stirring desolate, or melodious, and other characteristics. It shows the simple and honest temperament of the working people of all nationalities in Hebei Province. Most are to depict real life, but also some are to praise historical figures. For thousands of years, tens of thousands of folk songs have been spread in Hebei province. They are closely accompanied by history and vividly record the life, labor, and struggle of the people in Hebei. The folk songs of the province can be roughly divided into five styles, namely: Central Hebei Plain region; western Taihang Mountain region, part of northeast Hebei Chengde region, northern Zhangjiakou region, and southern Hebei region. The folk songs in these areas have their characteristics in terms of tone, genre, style, singing and so on. Among them, the folk songs of the central Hebei Plain in Hebei have the most strong local flavor.</i></p>

Introduction

According to recent archeological discoveries, Chinese folk music dates back 7,000 years. Not only in form but also artistic conception, China has been home to a colorful culture of folk music. Chinese folk music is largely based on the pentatonic scale and differs from traditional Western music in that it also pays more attention to the form of expression. Traditional Han weddings and funerals usually include a type of oboe called suona and percussive ensembles called chuigushou. Ensembles of harmonicas (sheng), shawms (suona), flutes (dizi), and percussion instruments (especially yunluo gongs) are popular in northern villages; their music derives from the imperial temple music of Beijing, Xi'an, Wutai shan, and Tianjin. Xi'an drum music, which consists of wind and percussion instruments, is popular around Xi'an and has gained some commercial popularity outside China. Another important instrument is the sheng, or pipe, an ancient instrument that is the forerunner of all Western free reed instruments, such as the accordion. Parades led by Western brass bands are common and often rival a shawm or chuigushou band in volume. In southern Fujian and Taiwan, nanyin or nanguan is a genre of traditional ballads. They are sung by a woman, accompanied by a xiao and a pipa, and other traditional instruments. The music is generally sad and about a woman with heartbreak. Further south, in Shantou, the Hakka areas, and Chaozhou, Erxian and Zheng ensembles are popular. Sizhu ensembles use flutes and string or plucked instruments to make harmonious and melodious music that has become popular with some listeners in the West. They are popular in Nanjing and Hangzhou as well as elsewhere in the southern Yangtze River area. Sizhu has been secularized in the cities but remains spiritual in rural areas. Jiangnan sizhu (silk and bamboo music from Jiangnan) is a type of instrumental music often played by amateur musicians in teahouses in Shanghai; it has also become widely known outside its place of origin. Guangdong music or Cantonese music is instrumental music from Guangzhou and surrounding areas. It is based on the music of the Yueju (Cantonese opera), along with new compositions from the 1920s onward. Many pieces show influences of jazz and western music and use syncopation and triple time. This music tells stories and myths, perhaps even legends.

About Hebei Folk Song

As the "text of the nature of heaven and earth" and "the sound of the folk temperament", the Hebei folk song has always truly and vividly recorded the life of the people of Hebei and expressed their ideals and emotions. Today, while vigorously carrying forward the modern music culture, we should understand and master the regional distribution and artistic characteristics of Hebei folk songs in detail, which has great practical significance for the inheritance, development, and creation of Hebei folk songs with national spirit and distinct local characteristics.

Folk songs are the most direct and true reflection of people's social life, thoughts, and emotions, and they are an important part of folk music. The three basic characteristics of folk songs are 1. Folk songs are the most direct and close connection in people's social life; 2. The creation process of folk songs and their singing is

inseparable; 3. The production of folk songs has gone through a long and difficult process. Hebei folk songs have a long history, with unique, rich cultural and artistic deposits and strong local color. Because Hebei has unique geographical conditions, whether it is the plateau in the north, the vast plain, the long coastline of the Bohai Sea, or the rolling Taihang Mountain, is the beautiful cradle of Hebei folk songs. Hebei folk songs also have rich and colorful local dialects and diverse themes. In terms of tone, although Hebei folk songs are mainly five tones, they are also accompanied by six tones and seven tones, and some special tones, which make the folk music sound colorful. As for the aesthetic characteristics of Hebei folk songs, four aspects can be summarized from the development course of Hebei culture and Hebei art and culture: 1. Hebei folk songs are rich in language and wide in content. The language of Hebei is the most prominent among the provinces and cities, and the phonetic changes are rich and colorful, such as the Northeast dialect and the Shanxi dialect, which all appear in the region of Hebei. The lyrics of Hebei folk songs contain rich language connotations. Most of the lyrics of these folk songs are straightforward, well-structured, simple and simple, unmodified, and sometimes mixed with interesting dialects, reflecting the simplicity and frankness of the working people in Hebei. 2. Hebei folk songs are undulating and beautiful. Influenced by the language tone of the north, Hebei folk songs have obvious ups and downs, and high and bright melodies, showing the rhythm beauty which is different from other scattered rhythm. 3. Hebei folk songs are diverse in structure and widely spread. The sentence patterns of Hebei folk songs are five-character, seven-character, four-character, eight-character, nine-character, cross-sentence, etc., with various structures, not sticking to one pattern. Some also add a variety of modifying words, which enriches the structure of the lyrics. But on the whole, mainly the lyrics of the seven-character sentences, from the overall paragraph structure and sentence paragraph structure, also the seven-character sentences are more distinctive. For example, in Hebei Yanshan folk song-four seasons song: spring to peach blossom red, the people's commune is busy spring plowing, members work together, the sister driving a tractor, deep plowing deep flat ah, fast tillage fast sowing, striving for a good agricultural harvest. 4. Hebei folk songs are loud, clear and beautiful. Hebei folk songs are influenced by local dialects, and a large part of the tone is consistent with the trend of the local dialect. The pronunciation is relatively flat, and the ending is mostly used to sound. Compared with other local folk songs, they show simple but not oily, with direct feelings, and tune. At the same time, the use of lining words, lining cavity, and the modification of the cavity also reflect the lively and funny side of Hebei folk songs.

Hebei folk songs bearing the past dynasties Hebei people's life emotion and ideal, not only known as the "nature" of heaven and earth but also has the "ring of folk temperament" reputation, the real and vivid lyrics, the melody of beautiful and melodious, let a song of Hebei folk songs in the era of carrying forward modern music culture show Hebei folk songs. Based on a detailed understanding of the characteristics of Hebei folk songs, The researcher further analyzes their regional characteristics and artistic characteristics, and pays attention to the inheritance and development of Hebei folk songs, especially the songs with distinctive local characteristics or national spirit, and the songs also provide useful opinions for the creation of Hebei folk songs.

During the 14th Five-Year Plan period, the artistic inheritance of Hebei folk songs should be based on the blueprint of national cultural construction and the deployment of comprehensive cultural protection and inheritance. In the social development advancing with The Times, the development plan should take the path of inheritance route, and continuously promote the development of Hebei folk songs art, and culture. Especially in the background of the current vigorous development of information technology, the inheritance and development of Hebei folk songs should meet the needs of The Times, meet the aesthetic appreciation of the masses, follow the law of cultural development, and fully promote the artistic inheritance and cultural development of Hebei folk songs by relying on the teaching platform of the school.

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1 = $\text{F} \frac{2}{4}$ 小放牛 (河北民歌)

$\overset{\frown}{\underline{6 \cdot 1}} \ 5 \mid \overset{\frown}{\underline{6 \cdot 1}} \ 5 \mid \underline{3 \cdot 5} \ \underline{6 \dot{1}} \mid \underline{5643} \ 2 \mid \overset{\frown}{\underline{5323}} \ \overset{\frown}{\underline{553}} \mid \overset{\frown}{\underline{25}} \ \overset{\frown}{\underline{32}} \mid$

天 上 妙 楞 什 么 人 来 裁？ 地 下 的 那 个 黄 河
 天 上 妙 楞 王 母 娘 裁。 地 下 的 那 个 黄 河
 赵 州 桥 什 么 人 来 修？ 玉 石 的 那 个 栏 杆
 赵 州 桥 春 班 师 傅 修。 玉 石 的 那 个 栏 杆

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什 么 人 来 开？ 什 么 人 把 守 三 关 口？ 什 么 人 那 个
 老 龙 王 开。 杨 六 郎 把 守 三 关 口。 韩 香 子
 什 么 人 来 留？ 什 么 人 骑 驴 桥 上 过？ 什 么 人 那 个
 古 人 把 它 留。 张 果 老 骑 驴 桥 上 过。 荣 世 宗

$\overset{\frown}{\underline{25}} \ \overset{\frown}{\underline{32}} \mid \overset{\frown}{\underline{1 \cdot 2}} \ \overset{\frown}{\underline{35}} \mid \overset{\frown}{\underline{2327}} \ \overset{\frown}{\underline{6561}} \mid 5 - \mid \overset{\frown}{\underline{335}} \ \overset{\frown}{\underline{32}} \mid \overset{\frown}{\underline{34}} \ \overset{\frown}{\underline{32}} \mid$

出 家 未 曾 回 来 嘛 噫 哎 哎 哎 哟？ 推 上 去 退 下 来
 出 家 未 曾 回 来 嘛 噫 哎 哎 哎 哟。 推 上 去 退 下 来
 推 车 碾 下 一 道 沟 来 嘛 噫 哎 哎 哎 哟？
 推 车

$\overset{\frown}{\underline{335}} \ \overset{\frown}{\underline{32}} \mid \overset{\frown}{\underline{34}} \ \overset{\frown}{\underline{32}} \mid \overset{\frown}{\underline{25}} \ \overset{\frown}{\underline{32}} \mid \overset{\frown}{\underline{25}} \ \overset{\frown}{\underline{32}} \mid \overset{\frown}{\underline{1 \cdot 2}} \ \overset{\frown}{\underline{35}} \mid \overset{\frown}{\underline{2327}} \ \overset{\frown}{\underline{6561}} \mid 5 - \mid$

推 上 去。 退 下 来。 得 几 郎 当 得 几 郎 当 碾 下 一 道 沟 来 嘛 噫 哎 哎 哎 哟。

sunzp根据任桂珍演唱录音记谱, 欢迎指正。

Graph 1, Xiao Fangniu(Hebei Folk Song)

Hebei is a province with large folk music resources, while Hebei folk songs are representative of folk music varieties with unique cultural connotations. As a form of music, the essence of Hebei folk songs is a way for the people in all regions of Hebei province to take their voice as a means to express their views on the world and their world outlook and values formed in the specific "cultural and ecological environment". Therefore, the Hebei folk songs in high school music courses will able to put the Hebei folk song aesthetic tendency, aesthetic ideal, and each area in Hebei province human groups in the specific "cultural ecological environment" formed by the view of the world and world outlook and values to students, make the aesthetic emotion and the cultural character level of immersion and edification, make it set up for the correct view of yanzhao music culture.

Hebei Folk Song Choir Conductor's Role Model

The facets of Hebei Folk Song Choir leadership include two dimensions. There are several dimensions the researcher could have chosen, but these seem most helpful. The 'focus' dimension ranges from a focus on the organization (community/group) to a focus on the music; at one extreme, the music is a means to an end, at the other, it is an end in itself. The other dimension deals with an ethos that relates to the pursuit of participation or achievement. Following the 4-quadrant model used by Olivier and James and Arroba, The researcher has used these dimensions to create four different choral conducting styles, and the researcher has given each a name to make it more accessible. The researcher points out, however, and echoes the caveat mentioned in James and Context's explanation-that creating such a model can lead to a simplistic notion of choral conductors fitting into

one style or another, when in fact the model must be viewed as dynamic; a skilled choral conductor will draw on aspects of all four quadrants at different times and in response to different situations. All people have access to all four characters. However, each individual has preferences for the characters they play. Just as an actor prefers a certain type of role. We too will have a preference for the roles we play as leaders". My observations and experiences with choral leaders over several years suggest that while they undoubtedly move between the four positions of the model, the way they do so varies from person to person depending on their preferences. The researcher hopes to explore and illuminate these preferences by using the model with aspiring choral directors as well as for my development. The four quadrants have been given names to express their different strengths and preferences. The upper left quadrant is where a musical focus combines with a desire to perform. In this position, the leader pays attention to activity - designing new performances or an ever-increasing level of excellence. The diagonal counterpart is the catalyst, who, like the conductor, is action-oriented but has a purpose beyond the purely musical. The bottom left is the Organizer, who looks to maintain system and order, with strengths in administration and management. The quadrant on the upper right, where the focus on music meets the values of participation, The researcher has named (for lack of a more appropriate name) The Muse, which is concerned with the long-term well-being of the musical group. The two diagonally opposite positions share a desire for stability, while the right-hand positions reflect a desire for change. The top two positions are both primarily concerned with music, while the bottom two are concerned with organization or community. The right-hand roles are also interrelated, as both muse and catalyst require a high level of empathy as well as interpersonal and influencing skills, while the conductor and organizer positions require a high level of attention to detail and technicalities. In the diagram below, The researcher has provided some of the characteristics of each preference.

Music Education with Hebei Folk Songs

One of the steps taken in the years of independence to reorganize and develop education at the national level is the content of music education at all levels of the continuing education system, as in all walks of life. enriched with information and artifacts. This is evidenced by the state educational standards and curricula developed and implemented in general education schools for the subject of "music culture", the main formative stage of the educational system, based on the textbooks prepared on this basis. Scan In this way, the young generation will have the opportunity to become familiar with the history of national music, its stages of development, national characteristics, performance styles, and traditions, as well as the work of artists who have made a significant contribution to the development of national music. Assessing the development of society and the spiritual maturity of the individual, the examples of the national musical heritage, and the ideas contained therein. Today, the social order sets certain tasks for educational institutions in our country to continue the quality and effectiveness of education at a new level, to further expand the scope and continuous improvement of its content and essence. to more effectively use the national musical heritage in esthetic education, to pay more attention to works imbued with universal ideas that express in their content the unique way of life and psyche of our people. This in itself is an in-depth study of the content of folk music, which occupies a significant place in the heritage of folk music, the extensive use of its potential for educational purposes, the development of students, and its uniqueness. Characteristics, the in-depth acquaintance with the traditions, the performance styles in every respect, and, finally, the development of skills and abilities to perform them. Therefore, work on the use of folk music, which is an invaluable treasure of Hebei folk music, for the development of pedagogical and spiritual-moral means, scientific research in the country, as well as general secondary education. The study and analysis of the situation with examples of folk music heritage in general education schools is the subject of our research work. created the need for scientific research on more effective methods of learning in general education schools. For its part, the scientific research of folk music folklore provides a theoretical, practical, scientific-methodical, and didactic basis for the development of the spiritual and moral qualities of students through folk songs and their use in the educational system. The study of music education should focus on the study of folk songs in the teaching of music in general secondary schools, to improve the ideological, artistic, spiritual, and esthetic education of students. the lib is coming. However, the theoretical analysis and the study of the activities of general education high schools have shown that there are certain deficiencies in the use of folk song examples in the teaching of "music culture" and their involvement in the spirituality of students. This is because folk songs are not given enough space in the music programs and textbooks of secondary schools, and they are not provided with sources that can provide brief information about the traditions and forms of performance and the spirituality of students through folk songs. -the development of moral values is reflected in the lack of a specific methodological system. Our study aims to counteract these shortcomings, as it guarantees the relevance of the chosen topic. The age in which we live is the age of rapid scientific and technological revolution, which is also reflected in folk art. Hebei folk music, like other forms of folklore, is artistic and ideological, simple in content, concise and perfect, with many historical facts, because folk music is the basis of professional music. Children's folk music and children's songs, which connect the spiritual world of adults and children, also play an important

role in the treasury of folk music heritage. These songs are characterized by the unique expression of the life and psyche of children, various children's games, stories, and tales.

Hebei choral singing for sustaining psychological wellbeing

Table one Survey on Hebei choral singing for sustaining psychological wellbeing

	N	1	2	3	4	5
		Low				High
Enjoy life	1112	0.2	1.3	15.1	67.2	16.3
Life is meaningful	1097	0.7	2.8	17.5	54.3	24.6
Able to concentrate	1111	0.1	1.9	31.6	56.9	9.5
Accept bodily appearance	1113	1.1	4.5	18.3	51.8	24.3
Satisfaction with self	1108	0.9	4.7	21.1	60.3	13.0
Frequency of negative feelings	1112	0.7	5.4	27.7	54.9	11.2

Items are scaled such that high scores reflect high wellbeing. For the frequency of negative feelings item, for example, a high score means that the frequency of negative feelings was low (1 = always, 2 = very often, 3 = quite often, 4 = seldom, 5 = never).

The numerical data from the questionnaire were analyzed using SPSS 16. Principal component analysis was conducted on 24 singing items from the total sample and six country/gender groups. The results of the analysis of the first unrotated component provided the basis for constructing the following scale 12-item scale to assess the health effects of choral singing.

Comparisons between males and females in each country and between males and females in the total sample were made using independent t-tests. Independent t-tests were used. Product moment correlations were calculated between the Singing Scale and the WHOQOL.

Product moment correlations were calculated between the Singing Scale and the WHOQOL-BREF Mental Health Scale. To explore more specifically

To explore more specifically the issues addressed in this survey, we note the relatively small number of comments written by respondents on the questionnaire.

To explore more specifically the issues addressed in this survey, we note the comments written on the questionnaire by respondents who scored low on the Mental Health Scale but high on the WHOQOL-BREF Mental Health Scale.

Comments are written on the questionnaire by respondents who scored low on the Singing scale but high on the Singing scale. A simple thematic approach was used to identify examples that might explain life challenges.

Examples of life challenges that might explain relatively low levels of well-being were identified. Possible mechanisms linking singing to beneficial outcomes of well-being were also identified.

Conclusion

The study helps to build an evidence base to support greater public investment in Hebei Folk Song community music and singing services by local government and health authorities.

Greater public investment in community music and singing by local government and health authorities is called for.

Promoting well-being and health, especially after middle age, given

Worldwide, increasing life expectancy has led to continuing demographic change.

Whereas worldwide, increasing life expectancy has led to a continuing increase in the proportion of older people in national populations, there is a need to

revisit the opportunities available to help encourage people to remain physically, socially, and mentally active in retirement.

Staying active socially and spiritually. This paper argues that in all these respects, singing is a valuable activity.

In all of these respects, Hebei Folk Choir singing is a valuable activity that should be more widely recognized.

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